

FutuRSI: the Conception of a German Research Software Institution¹

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The FutuRSI project develops both a strategy and a concrete plan for implementing a research software institution in Germany. This institution is intended to contribute significantly to embedding the German research software ecosystem in the existing regional and international framework while simultaneously facilitating the required cultural change in the handling of research software.

Background: Research software – software created during the research process or for a research purpose – is today an indispensable element of scientific work in large parts of research. At the same time, it has special technical and professional requirements, is often developed without formally acquired software competencies, and is of subordinate interest to the commercial market. This often makes the long-term reproducibility of scientific results as well as the unimpeded reuse and sustainable further development of research software difficult. Additionally, the scientific system still offers few incentives for researchers to make research software sustainably available for broad use. Systemic efficiency and quality improvements as well as changed incentive structures at individual, organizational and technical levels therefore harbor the great potential to improve the development and use of research software in Germany [1]. However, a comprehensive strategy for the long-term design of the research software ecosystem in Germany is currently lacking. This paper aims to provide the impetus for corresponding strategy development and is thus a building block that describes how the German science system can meet the digital transformation in general and also the rapid developments in the field of artificial intelligence in the area of research software [2].

Connection Points: Funding bodies have so far primarily focused on the availability of research data, particularly through the initiative to build the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). Research data and research software are related but also clearly distinguish-

able, e.g., in terms of their creation or quality assurance. For research software, orchestrated knowledge transfer between technical disciplines is also helpful, which could be particularly well supported by overarching structures such as community organization. Against the backdrop of discussions about the sovereignty and security of science in the digital realm, the German Science and Humanities Council (“Wissenschaftsrat”) therefore proposes examining the establishment of such structures that treat software as an integral part of the entire research infrastructure [3]. The British Software Sustainability Institute is cited as a model, which is jointly supported by all relevant British research funding organizations. The Netherlands eScience Center, established in 2012, also bundles expertise in research software development and research software community management in a national center and thus plays a significant role in the Dutch scientific system. These examples impressively show that the desirable synergies in research software (further) development can only be achieved through cooperation between *Research Software Engineers* (RSEs) and users and that a centralized actor can generate high visibility for the topic of research software and effectively advance necessary systemic adaptations [1,4].

Challenges: The research software ecosystem in Germany is characterized by systemic deficits that impair the quality and reproducibility of scientific results and lead to inefficiencies as well as the loss of valuable expertise. Lack of basic research on the use, development and impact of research software also makes it difficult to assess these deficits and thus the strategic further development of the field. First, the quality and reusability of research software is in need of improvement. Software products could be upgraded with existing quality assurance procedures such as testing or benchmarking procedures. Actors are needed who offer the research software community an organizational structure, e.g., in supporting users and developers or in building services for dealing with research software. Services for overcoming everyday obstacles such as licensing or publication of research software must be established and permanently financed. Important research software also needs long-term financial support, as well as the structured governance necessary for prioritization and selection. Second, the training and

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continuing education of researchers in early career phases to become RSEs is currently not organized or standardized, or only to a small extent. Ultimately, knowledge acquisition therefore usually takes place individually and thus sometimes very unstructured and with varying effectiveness. Training courses, consulting services, networking between users and providers of research software, workshops or exchange forums could remedy this deficiency. Third, there is a lack of recognition of development performance, which makes an independent career path as an RSE within the scientific system difficult. What is needed is a change in awareness that research software is not a by-product. Certifications and reviews of research software, awards, and an accredited curriculum would be desirable. Fourth, improved work environment structures for RSEs are needed, e.g., through the establishment of semi-stable teams or central RSE units [5]. However, the heterogeneous scientific system in Germany makes rapid adaptations difficult. A professional spokesperson in the institutional structure could create appropriate support services, guarantee advocacy, and spread local successes as a coordinating actor.

Solution Proposal: To address these challenges, FutuRSI conceives an institution for research software in Germany. As an umbrella of a network, the institution could support existing local or organization-specific units in the field of research software. This research software institution could also disseminate proven practices, develop community standards, and facilitate cooperation between scientific disciplines. In addition, the institution could also allocate funds, e.g., in the form of fellowships or through a research software maintenance fund. Furthermore, accompanying research on the topic of research software could also be located here. A German research software institution could, in this future vision, serve as a central coordination point (“Hub”) connecting regional, local or organization-specific competence centers, groups, units and organizations (“Spokes”). Such a structure would respect the federal character of the German scientific system while enabling effective national coordination with strong local anchoring.

Project Vision: The **FutuRSI** project, currently funded by the Klaus Tschira Foundation, helps shape Germany’s future research software

ecosystem by facilitating cooperation between research institutions and areas, coordinating services and offerings, and strengthening and connecting the people who develop research software. The project involves cooperation between ^athe Society for Research Software in Germany (de-RSE e.V.), ^bthe German Informatics Society (GI e.V.), ^cJülich Research Centre (Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH), ^dthe Helmholtz-Center Dresden-Rossendorf (Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf e.V.), ^ethe Competence Center Digital Research at University Jena (zedif) and ^fthe Göttingen State and University Library (Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Göttingen). The central task of FutuRSI is to develop a concrete concept for a German research software institution in order to accompany the cultural change in dealing with research software in Germany at a strategic and organizational level.

Learn more at [FutuRSI.de](https://www.futursi.de).

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